

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 6.4

Horizon Europe Programme
HORIZON-CL6-2022-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement No°101081883.

Start date of project: 1st December 2022

Duration: 48 months

D6.4 Summary of exploitation workshops for knowledge transfer

Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows

Deliverable details	
Work Package Title	Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination
Task Number	6.4
Deliverable Number	6.4
Deliverable Title	Summary of exploitation workshops for knowledge transfer
Revision Number	V2
Responsible Organisation	C.I.P. Citizens in Power
Author(s)	Maria Christodoulou
Due Date	Saturday, May 31, 2025
Delivered Date	Saturday, May 31, 2025
Reviewed by	MOVERIM
Dissemination level	PU
Please cite as	Christodoulou, M., D6.4 Summary of exploitation workshops for knowledge transfer, 2025, P2Green Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu
Contact person EC	Sofia Pacchini

Contributing partners	
1.	AGRATHAER GMBH – Germany (Coordinator)
2.	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV – Germany
3.	VILLE DE PARIS – France
4.	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN – Ireland
5.	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET - Sweden
6.	COPENHAGEN BUSINESS SCHOOL - Denmark

7.	LUONNONVARAKESKUS - Finland
8.	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND MAYNOOTH - Ireland
9.	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - Greece
10.	BIOAZUL, SL - Spain
11.	CIP CITIZENS IN POWER - Cyprus
12.	ECOVILLAGE HANNOVER – Germany (terminated)
13.	GOLDEIMER GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH - Germany
14.	INSTITUT D'ARQUITECTURA AVANCADA DE CATALUNYA - Spain
15.	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH) - Germany
16.	FUNDACION CENTRO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONES DEL AGUA - Spain
17.	SUN GLOBAL CHEMICALS SERVICES SL - Spain
18.	IRIDRA SRL - Italy
19.	ECOLE NATIONALE DES PONTS ET CHAUSSEES - France
20.	KOZGAZDASAG- ES REGIONALIS TUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT - Hungary
21.	HAFENCITY UNIVERSITAT HAMBURG - Germany
22.	SUSTCHEM TECHNIKI SYMVOULEFTIKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA - Greece
23.	TRANSITION APS - Denmark
24.	TRIODOS BANK NV - Netherlands
25.	MOVERIM SRL - Belgium
26.	SOCIEDAD AGRARIA DE TRANSFORMACION TROPS N 2803 DE RESPONSABILIDAD LIMITADA - Spain
27.	AGRI SMART DATA – Spain (terminated)
28.	TOUCH DOWN GOTLAND AB - Sweden
29.	SANITATION360 AB - Sweden

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 6.4

30.	GOTLANDS BRYGGERI AB - Sweden
31.	AGUAS Y SANEAMIENTOS DE LA AXARQUIA SA - Spain
32.	VunaNexus - Switzerland
33.	KREISWERKE BARNIM GMBH - Germany
34	AGUALYTICS TECNOLOGICA DEL AGUA S.L. - Spain

D6.4

Contents

D6.4.....	4
1 Executive Summary	8
2 Summary of Exploitation Workshops for Knowledge Transfer	9
2.1 Description	9
2.2 Introduction	9
3 1 st Exploitation Workshop in Malaga: Identification and initial assessment of KERs within the P2GreenN project	11
3.1 Workshop Structure and Timeline	11
3.2 Summary of Group Discussions.....	12
3.3 Outcomes from the 1 st Exploitation Workshop	14
4 2 nd Exploitation Workshop, Gotland, Sweden: Key Exploitable Results and their Impacts.....	16
4.1 Partner Survey prior to the workshop on Exploitation	16
4.2 Workshop Structure and Timeline	17
4.3 Summary of Thematic Discussions	18
4.3.1 Technology development.....	18
4.3.2 Replication Actions	18
4.3.3 Legal Framework and Market Analysis	19
4.4 Outcomes from the 2 nd Exploitation Workshop	20
5 3 rd Exploitation Workshop, Müncheberg, Germany: Reassessment of existing KERs, Identification of Gaps and Development of New KERs	21
5.1 Partner Survey prior to the workshop on Exploitation	21
5.2 Workshop structure and timeline.....	22
5.3 Summary of Group Discussions.....	23
5.3.1 Group 1 - KER Validation.....	23
5.3.2 Group 2 - New KERs Identification	24
5.3.3 Group 3 - Pathway Definition	25
5.4 Comparative Analysis of Discussion Findings.....	26
5.5 Lessons learned from the 3 rd Exploitation Workshop.....	27

5.6	Positive Outcomes from the 3 rd Exploitation Workshop	28
6	Exploitation Plan	29
6.1	KER identification.....	29
6.2	KERs Technology Level Assessment	29
6.3	Exploitation Routes	35
6.4	Joint market analysis and IP protection strategies	37
7	Exploitation Roadmap	38
8	Outlook: 4 th Exploitation Workshop, online: Evaluation of Exploitation achievements 40	
9	Conclusion	41
10	References	42

Index of Figures

Figure 1	Group Discussion from 1st Exploitation Workshop.....	12
Figure 2	Picture of consortium during COM Malaga.....	15
Figure 3	- Group Discussion from 2nd Exploitation Workshop	17
Figure 4	Group Discussion from 3rd Exploitation Workshop	22
Figure 5	Group Discussion from 3rd Exploitation Workshop	23
Figure 6	KER progress as of M30 (May 2025)..	30
Figure 7	P2Green Exploitation Roadmap (M12-M48).....	38
Figure 8	P2Green Exploitation Roadmap.	39
Figure 9	EW4 agenda overview, Online, June 2026 (M42). Lead: CIP & Moverim	40

Index of Tables

Table 1 – Glossary	7
Table 2 - Key Exploitable Results	11

Glossary	
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMC	Business Model Canvas
CBMC	Circular Business Model Canvas
COM	Consortium Meeting
EU	European Union
GA	Grand Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
KER	Key Exploitable Results
ML	Machine Learning
WP	Work Package
BREEAM	Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method
CCRI	Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
CIP	Citizens in Power
Copa Cogeca	European association of farmers and agricultural cooperatives
DG ENV	Directorate-General for Environment (European Commission)
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
ESPP	European Sustainable Phosphorus Platform
EurEau	European Federation of National Associations of Water Services
KRAV	Swedish organic farming certification label
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RBA	Resource by Agenda (EU cluster network)
RP	Reporting Period
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

EC	European Commission
EWA	European Water Association
IWA	International Water Association
N&P	Nitrogen and Phosphorus
R&D	Research and Development

Table 1 – Glossary

1 Executive Summary

As part of the Exploitation Strategy for the P2Green project, WP6 has held 3 Exploitation Workshops aiming at the identification, completion, and advancement of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) as stated in the Grant Agreement (GA).

The KERs refer to Exploitable Results that would advance the project's progress and enable follower regions and end users to benefit from P2Green's solutions. In detail, these KERs refer to:

KER1: Development of blueprints from P2Green pilot regions; is a responsibility of Work Package (WP)1. This result will be utilised by replication sites and will benefit farmers, authorities, and researchers.

KER2: Methodologies and criteria for data collection in P2Green; is a responsibility of WP2. This result will be used to enhance in-house expertise, and it will benefit scientific communities.

KER3: Toolbox for Social Acceptance; is a responsibility of WP3. This result will be used internally to facilitate societal acceptance and will eventually benefit civil society, farmers, and municipalities.

KER4: Development of a sustainable governance framework for N & P management and recovery in the P2Green pilot regions; is a responsibility of WP4. This result aims to address the governance approach on projects similar to P2Green, and will benefit public authorities and policymakers at a local, national, and international level.

KER5: P2Green Replication/ Innovation Platform and Replication Action Plans for Front Runner Regions; is a responsibility of WP5. This result focuses on enabling other suitable areas to replicate P2Green's technologies and will benefit public authorities and policymakers at a local, national, and international level, as well as scientific communities.

KER6: Regional Replication Action Plans; is a responsibility of WP5. This result aims to exploit a simulation of the results, addressing public authorities and policymakers at a local, national, and international level, as well as scientific communities, to showcase the potential of P2Green's solutions.

KER7: Guide on how to initiate, manage, and scale circular solutions (report & workshops); is a responsibility of WP5. This result will be internally used and will benefit organisations considering partaking in partnerships involved with circular solutions.

For the completion of these KERs, a collaborative effort has been made by all partners to support the responsible WPs. To assist these efforts, an Exploitation Plan and an Exploitation Roadmap have been developed, where current actions and future actions are described.

Part of those actions include the 3 Exploitation Workshops, showing the KERs current state and their possibility of advancement. Findings from these workshops are given, showing current challenges, describing the governance framework, Intellectual Property strategies, and social acceptance. Important also has been the development of the 4 Circular Business Model Canvases (CBMC) for the 3 pilot regions, and the possibility of an additional CBMC focusing on the Replication/ Innovation Platform, which would expand the revenue streams for P2Green's partners.

2 Summary of Exploitation Workshops for Knowledge Transfer

2.1 Description

This deliverable falls under the Exploitation Plan (D6.4), aiming to identify Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and lead partners in the development of their exploitation, as well as their exploitation routes. In addition, the technology level assessment of KERs will be included in the Plan. The annual exploitation workshops will supplement the Exploitation Plan. They will help to identify the Key Exploitable Results and conduct a joint market analysis to identify the commercialization potential for relevant consortium members and specify the required IP protection measures. This Plan is related to T6.1.

2.2 Introduction

The P2Green project aims to foster sustainable circular economy practices across Europe by developing and promoting innovative solutions for nutrient recovery and reuse. The exploitation workshops conducted as part of this initiative play a crucial role in identifying, refining, and strategising the deployment of Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The KERs, as outlined in the Grant Agreement, are shown in Table 2. These workshops are designed to facilitate knowledge transfer, enhance market readiness, and align with EU policies, ultimately contributing to the bioeconomy. Through these workshops, participants develop their understanding of exploitation and transition from research-based models to product-based models. As part of the Exploitation Plan, the completion of the KERs will allow the P2Green Consortium to replicate the findings to follower regions, address major gaps in regulations, and commercialise solutions that utilise waste. In this document, a detailed summary of each Exploitation Workshop can be found. Additionally, the Exploitation Plan is outlined, and an Exploitation Roadmap is drafted.

Key Exploitable Results				
WP	Key Exploitable Result	IPR Owner(s)	Potential Exploitation	Potential Users
1	Development of blueprints from P2Green pilot regions	All	Farmers, authorities, researchers and civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs, associations, etc.).	Potential of replication in other sites
2	Methodologies and criteria for data collection in P2Green	All	Scientific communities	In-house expertise, replication of data for new R&D projects.
3	Toolbox for Social Acceptance	All	Civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs, associations, etc.), farmers and farmers' associations, municipalities	Internal use to increase societal acceptance within their networks
4	Development of a sustainable governance framework for N & P management and recovery in the P2Green pilot regions	All	Public Authorities, Policy makers at local, national and international level	Replication of the P2Green governance approach
5	P2Green Replication/ Innovation Platform and Replication Action Plans for Front Runner Regions	All	Public authorities, policy makers at local, national and international level, scientific communities	Replication of the P2Green project in other suitable areas
5	Regional Replication Action Plans	All	Public authorities, policy makers at local, national and international level, scientific communities	Exploitation of the simulation results / open source data

Key Exploitable Results				
WP	Key Exploitable Result	IPR Owner(s)	Potential Exploitation	Potential Users
5	Guide on how to initiate, manage and scale circular solutions (report & workshops)	All	Organisations considering to initiate or already taking part in a partnership within circular solutions	Exploitation for in-house expertise

Table 2 - Key Exploitable Results

3 1st Exploitation Workshop in Malaga: Identification and initial assessment of KERs within the P2Green project

The 1st Exploitation Workshop in Malaga focused on delineating the potential and applications of the KERs identified by the P2Green project. The primary goal was to understand how these results could be harnessed by various stakeholders to foster sustainable development and policy innovation.

3.1 Workshop Structure and Timeline

The P2Green 1st Exploitation Workshop took place in Malaga, Spain, during the 2nd Consortium Meeting (COM) in October 2023. In order to engage as many participants as possible, the workshop was held in a hybrid mode. Therefore, all project's partners had the opportunity to participate in the workshop. The workshop was divided into 3 segments, which included first an introduction to pilot regions' technologies, as well as the KERs. Then, through group discussions, the targets for each KER were set, and discussions on the potential for exploitation, commercialization, and scale-up of the technologies were held. Following these conversations, the third segment of the workshop included a presentation from partners from ICLEI and CBS on "Market analysis, available funding sources and grants and subsidies", in an effort to familiarise partners with the concepts of commercialisation and investment strategies.

3.2 Summary of Group Discussions

Figure 1 Group Discussion from 1st Exploitation Workshop

Following an explanation of the purposes of the KERs and a description of their role for each Work Package (WP), partners addressed discussions, followed by identifying how those KERs will be measured and what they mean for each WP. A summary of each KER's meaning and measuring framework is given and reflects the status quo of the first Exploitation Workshop in October 2023.

KER1: Blueprints from P2Green pilot regions

Exploitation Routes: Utilization in new projects, policy development, and training programs.

Technology Level Assessment: Advanced; ready for implementation and replication

This KER is aimed at stakeholders, including young local government officials, Green Deal enthusiasts, real estate developers, engineers, rural municipalities, and farmers. These blueprints serve as foundational documents for initiating new projects, developing policies, and providing training for SMEs. The blueprints can also be used to secure service contracts that replicate successful models in new contexts.

KER2: Methodologies and Criteria for Data Collection in P2Green

Exploitation Routes: Academic research, AI/ML algorithm development, and consultancy services.

Technology Level Assessment: Intermediate; requires further validation and refinement.

Targeted at stakeholders such as educational institutions, researchers, consultants, and environmental agencies, this KER facilitates research and project development. The

methodologies support the creation of AI/ML algorithms that can enhance data-driven decision-making processes.

KER3: Guide on How to Initiate, Manage, and Scale Circular Solutions

Exploitation Routes: Policy development, educational resources, and regional replication.

Technology Level Assessment: Advanced; applicable across various regions and sectors.

This guide is essential for green authorities, academia, business actors, organic farming associations, regional governments, and organizations like Greenpeace. It provides insights for policy inspiration, educational use, and enabling regions to replicate successful circular economy models.

KER4: P2Green Replication Platform and Replication Action Plans

Exploitation Routes: Educational purposes, project initiation, and synergy creation.

Technology Level Assessment: Intermediate; platform development in progress.

This KER is crucial for wastewater operators, urban solid waste managers, and golf federations. It supports new projects and educational initiatives by creating synergies with other sustainability projects.

KER5: Toolbox for Social Acceptance

Exploitation Routes: Communication strategies, research, and knowledge transfer.

Technology Level Assessment: Intermediate; requires field testing for effectiveness.

Designed for decision-makers and companies, particularly in pharmaceuticals and SMEs, this toolbox aids in developing communication plans, conducting research, and transferring knowledge to foster public acceptance and support for circular economy initiatives.

KER6: Sustainable Governance Framework for N & P Management

Exploitation Routes: Policy formulation, governance models, and planning support.

Technology Level Assessment: Advanced; ready for adoption by local and regional authorities.

This framework targets universities, local and regional governments, and wastewater authorities. It aids in policy development and system planning, supporting nitrogen and phosphorus recovery.

KER7: Regional Replication Action Plans

Exploitation Routes: Policy guidelines, stakeholder engagement, and replication support.

Technology Level Assessment: Intermediate; pilot testing underway.

These plans are designed for national and regional development agencies and stakeholders, providing guidelines to engage policymakers and promote stakeholder involvement.

3.3 Outcomes from the 1st Exploitation Workshop

In summary, during the 1st Exploitation Workshop, partners had the opportunity to identify the KERs and set tangible measures for their completion. As part of this first workshop, participants also had the opportunity to learn about the importance of commercialisation and the means of funding that would help enhance their actions and future pathways. From the unfolded discussions, as partners understood the meaning of the KERs, interests sparked, and anticipation for specific KERs was set. An important note was also given to the succession of each work package, as their progress influences the achievement of each KER, which is interrelated to the work of each work package, as shown in Table 2.

Partners showed significant interest in Stakeholder Engagement Methodology and Blueprints as were presented by CBS. They recognised the importance of collaboration and buy-in from various parties to ensure the success and sustainability of the project outcomes. As discussions deepened, interesting was also for the partners the creation of Circular Business Models that would promote sustainable and regenerative practices within the project and beyond. This also sparked discussions on Cost-Benefit Analysis and how to identify the most efficient way to turn P2Green's solutions to profitable companies.

Partners emphasised the importance of the development of Technical Tools and Guidelines, such as the Smart Fertigation Tool. They also underscored the importance of providing practical resources to support implementation and replication efforts and the need for specific fertiliser guidelines as well as the establishment of Soil Monitoring Protocols, to help monitor and link data gathering technologies.

Focusing then on Policy Recommendations, partners acknowledged the need for supportive regulatory frameworks to facilitate the adoption and scaling of project innovations. To achieve this, participants pointed out the need to assess the feasibility and market potential of project outcomes and summarise the available finance options for the implementation of the project's results. Alternative approaches and systems were also suggested to maximise project findings.

As discussions concluded, a very important mention was given to the Dissemination of the project's innovations to bring social acceptance and increase following. Participants

also emphasised the need to demonstrate the potential for reusing wastewater in various industries, like clothes production, and sparking new projects and initiatives, evaluating the societal impact of turning wastewater into valuable resources.

Figure 2 Picture of consortium during COM Malaga.

4 2nd Exploitation Workshop, Gotland, Sweden: Key Exploitable Results and their Impacts

The 2nd Exploitation Workshop, held during the 3rd COM in Gotland in May 2024 and utilising the World Café methodology, was designed to facilitate in-depth discussions, collaborative problem-solving, and the development of strategic exploitation plans for the P2Green project. This summary breaks down the survey conducted prior to the workshop, outlines the workshop schedule, and describes the ideas, structure, and results in detail.

4.1 Partner Survey prior to the workshop on Exploitation

Prior to the 2nd Exploitation Workshop, a survey was conducted among project partners to gather their thoughts on exploitation. The survey revealed several key insights:

- 1. Understanding of Exploitation:** The majority of respondents defined exploitation as the "utilisation and commercialization of project outcomes", focusing on the practical application and market integration of the results. Some participants also emphasized the exploration of new ideas and concepts, while a few noted concerns about potential unfair treatment for personal gain.
- 2. Promising Opportunities:** The survey identified several promising opportunities for exploiting the P2Green project results:
 - Optimization of Reclaimed Water Use: Particularly at TROPS partner farms, highlighting a direct application of project innovations.
 - Policy Advocacy and Regulation Influence: Creating a supportive regulatory environment to facilitate the adoption of new technologies.
 - Commercialization of Innovative Technologies: Bringing new products and processes to market.
 - Expansion to New Regions: Extending project activities to areas that can benefit from the innovations.
 - Industry Collaboration: Partnering with industry players to scale up and integrate project outcomes into commercial operations.
- 3. Significant Achievements:** The project had several notable achievements up to the point of the survey:
 - Implementation of Pilot Projects: Successful execution of initial test cases demonstrating the viability of project technologies.
 - Strategic Partnerships: Building alliances with key stakeholders to support project goals.
 - Stakeholder Engagement and Capacity Building: Effective involvement and training of relevant parties to ensure sustainable impact.
 - Increased Awareness: Dissemination activities that raised the profile of the project and its objectives.

4. **Challenges:** The major challenges identified were:
- Policy Advocacy and Regulation: Navigating complex regulatory landscapes to facilitate project adoption.
 - Industry Collaboration: Engaging with industry partners to achieve scale and integration.
 - Commercialisation: Moving innovative technologies from pilot stages to market readiness.
 - Financing and Local Resistance: Securing funding and overcoming resistance to new products in local markets.

4.2 Workshop Structure and Timeline

The 2nd Exploitation Workshop, held in Gotland, utilised the World Café methodology to foster in-depth discussions and collaborative problem-solving (Löhr, Weinhardt & Sieber, 2020). The main goals were to identify high-impact KERs, develop clear exploitation strategies, and strengthen stakeholder networks. Whilst in group discussions, participants had to develop visual maps which helped explore and define the relationships between the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and their broader implications within the bioeconomy. Visual mapping was used to help participant better conceptualise their ideas (Cabrera & Cabrera, 2018).

The workshop followed a well-structured time schedule designed to maximise engagement and productivity. The workshop was divided into 3 segments, starting with a presentation of the workshop's objectives, including the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and the development of strategic exploitation plans. Then partners were divided into 4 groups which were dove into discussions on KERs prioritisation, opportunity exploration, and challenges identification (Figure 3 **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). Following these conversations, partners presented their findings and engaged in full participants' discussion to synthesise insights and develop a collective strategy.

Figure 3 - Group Discussion from 2nd Exploitation Workshop

4.3 Summary of Thematic Discussions

4.3.1 Technology development

During discussions on technological developments as part of the project, partners emphasised the benefits of the Smart Fertigation Tool, like reduced fertiliser use, higher production efficiency, and water savings. What seemed to be the greatest challenges were the need for knowledge dissemination and investment for adoption. Similarly, with the Fertiliser Guidelines, according to the participants, those guidelines would help build trust with end users (e.g. farmers), while building competence, knowledge, and subsequently increasing the use of P2Green's solutions.

When addressing the benefits of the final fertiliser product, partners highlighted the market potential of the product, as it will provide an opportunity for users to reduce chemical fertiliser use and increase market competition between conventional fertilisers. Regardless of the benefits, partners found challenging the policy restrictions that limit the commercialisation routes of the products, a challenge that partners from WP3 were called to address during the following months (Results can be found e.g. in the upcoming D3.8). Part of the technologies developed is also the Soil Sampling and Monitoring Protocol that would primarily be used by researchers, including P2Green partners, to monitor soil health and the effects of the solutions trials.

Overall, from the technology development discussions, it was observed that partners understand the importance of the technological advancement of P2Green solutions and are aware of the challenges that need addressing. They are also able to identify end users for each solution and recognise the pathways to reach them.

4.3.2 Replication Actions

Regarding future replication actions, partners are focusing on the development of the P2Green Replication/ Innovation Platform, where all technologies used and explored during the project's lifespan are shared between partners. This tool is internal, and so far, only P2Green partners have access to its data. It is part of the P2Green website and the external part will grow with projects lifetime and its expanding results. This tool aims to allow follower regions to replicate pilot regions' work and explore more systems to achieve sustainable fertigation solutions. To foster the enhancement of the replication platform's content, partners at the time were performing feasibility studies in follower regions that examined all the possible ways P2Green's solutions can be implemented in those areas, and how end users and governments can be inspired to adopt these circular solutions. Challenges mentioned during the discussion were Intellectual Property (IP) rights, EU regulations, and commercialisation pathways for the platform itself.

Partners also discussed the possibility of discovering additional innovations based on their models that could address more gaps in the bioeconomy. This would also help raise awareness and increase social acceptance of P2Green's work. Additional research on more solutions based on sanitary waste would also contribute to the academic world, as well as provide farmers with additional solutions. These discussions generated a

conversation on potential new KERs, which were discussed during the 3rd Exploitation Workshop (Chapter 5.3.2). For the time being, these additional possibilities for new innovations were limited due to the restricted funding and low awareness of the need to develop more circular solutions.

A prime example of how P2Green solutions could be highlighted was given by our partners themselves with the production of their Beer, which is made out of wheat grown using P2Green fertilisers. With a thorough Cost-Benefit Analysis, enhancing the argument that this project's solutions are worth investing in and supporting, partners stressed that those products could be used as credentials and motives for end users and policymakers to accept and promote P2Green's solutions.

Overall, partners acknowledge the importance of creating an accessible environment for follower regions to replicate the project's technologies and continue the pilot regions' work. They also found it important to address possible new solutions that would cover more gaps in the bioeconomy chain, and promote P2Green's solutions, focusing on the end results and how those benefit the overall society.

4.3.3 Legal Framework and Market Analysis

During the 2nd Exploitation Workshop, participants had the opportunity to discuss the Legal Framework of P2Green's solutions and conduct a market analysis for potential commercialisation of P2Green's solutions. As shown from the discussions, at the time, regulatory barriers prevented P2Green solutions from commercialisation, as EU regulations did not approve the distribution of bio-fertilisers derived from human urine and human excreta.

Partners from WP3 were at the time in the process of collecting all routes to commercialisation based on EU and National Regulations. Partners were also trying to find ways to address these regulatory barriers with policy recommendations, which are presented at any given chance during open calls from the EU and policy-related events.

This was also an opportunity for partners to emphasise the need for dissemination material to be developed, addressing different stakeholders. Important was also to establish a common glossary that would help all partners communicate internally and externally using the same terminology. A "P2Green Glossary" was established and provided to partners during the following COM in Italy.

During the discussion on further Market Analysis, participants expressed their interest in establishing Circular Business Models focusing on P2Green's solutions, which was going to be addressed by Deliverable 3.1 Report containing four circular business models (Lasthein, Ekstrand, Møller, Stieber, Sargsyan, 2025), containing all the details on all possible commercialisation pathways for P2Green solutions.

To sum up, the discussions evolving around the legal framework and market analysis raised the need to address policymakers and regulatory barriers, while exploring all commercialisation pathways for P2Green solutions. While challenges exist, partners

remained positive that through P2Green's initiatives, all challenges would be addressed, and all possible solutions would be explored.

4.4 Outcomes from the 2nd Exploitation Workshop

During the 2nd Exploitation Workshop, conversations revolved around 3 main themes. Technology development, Replication actions, and Legal framework & Market analysis. Partners discussed the impact of their solutions, the affected communities, and the challenges they were facing. Important mention was given to the importance of the replication/ innovation platform, which will allow follower regions to replicate P2Green's solutions and expand the project's efforts.

Policymakers were also identified as an important point of the main discussions for the participants, as they were identified as the key enablers for the acknowledgment and acceptance of P2Green solutions. Strategies on how to approach them were very important and they included participation in policy events, development of flyers on Core messages addressing different policy-related stakeholders, participation in open calls/ consultation processes via ESPP, CCRI and "have your say" portal on EU regulations related to P2Green topics, and overall promotion of P2Green's solutions to raise awareness, attraction and overall market demand.

On the brighter side of the workshop, partners were intrigued to discuss potential new innovations using sanitary waste that could expand P2Green's solutions into different sectors. As the time did not allow for expansion of the conversation, partners agreed to revisit the topic during the 3rd Exploitation Workshop (see Chapter 5.3.2) and provide possible new innovations with the use of P2Green solutions.

Overall, the structured approach of the workshop, combined with the collaborative format of the World Café methodology, ensured a comprehensive and inclusive exploration of all thematics. The outcomes set a strong foundation for future steps and provided leverage for future discussions to help perform actions to engage a variety of stakeholders that would drive the project's success forward.

5 3rd Exploitation Workshop, Müncheberg, Germany: Reassessment of existing KERs, Identification of Gaps and Development of New KERs

The 3rd Exploitation Workshop was held in Müncheberg, Germany, during the 5th COM in May 2025. It was based on round table discussions aiming to address the overall KERs progression, highlight difficulties and gaps in the exploitation progress, and suggest actionable steps to address those gaps. The 3rd Exploitation Workshop was held as a follow-up from both previous workshops and as a conclusion to the overall discussions, finalising the remaining steps for the exploitation of the project during its life span.

The following summary highlights the key findings from the pre-exploitation survey, showcases the structure of the workshop, and describes the overall findings of the conversations held during the workshop.

5.1 Partner Survey prior to the workshop on Exploitation

To facilitate a better understanding of the discussion concepts and help participants prepare, a survey was distributed to the participants prior to the workshop aiming to grasp their understanding for the project's progress so far in meeting the KERs, as well as provide feedback on further practices that should be implemented to meet those KERs and achieve sufficient exploitation and dissemination of the project. The questionnaire consisted of 25 questions, from which the first 14 were related to the KERs technology assessment. More specifically, partners were asked to evaluate the progress of each KER on a scale from 1 to 5 and evaluate whether the direction taken to address them based on the 1st Exploitation Workshop was followed (see Chapter 3.3). The rest of the questionnaire's questions focused on the future actions that need to be taken to fully address the KERs. In more detail, the following insights were discovered.

- 1. Have KERs been met?:** Overall, from this survey's findings, we can assess that the KERs' progress is on track. The KERs have been met overall by 70%, signifying steady progress, yet emphasizing the need to more frequently address them.
- 2. What is the TRL of each Pilot Region?:** Based on participants' responses, the technology readiness level of each pilot region has almost been achieved with an overall level of approximately 73.33%.

In more detail, for the Swedish Pilot region, there is an approximate 72.89% met of the TRL. For the German Pilot region, TRL has been achieved at approximately 73.11%. Finally, the Spanish Pilot region has achieved approximately 75.67% TRL.

- 3. What do you believe is the KERs' current state?:** The KERs are progressing in a steady, efficient rhythm, but require more attentive monitoring during project meetings.

- 4. What additional actions should be taken to achieve satisfactory exploitation of P2Green?:** Participants highlighted the need to identify **the targeted audience** and disseminate **the results** of the project according to their needs. Specifically, they believe that better dissemination would be achieved if the overall promotion of the project focuses on the results and those results are described according to the key audiences' needs (e.g. farmers, public authorities, market). An important note was also given on identifying the legal pathways that need to be followed to grant access to follower regions to replicate the technologies and advance the project objectives, as well as allow the end products to be marketed around Europe. To do so, spreading the word to policymakers through event attendance and drafting of reports on the topic should be prioritized. In addition, shifting the dissemination strategy to a more result-based approach, promoting the pilot and follower regions' work, could potentially lead to more sufficient communication of the project's outcomes.

5.2 Workshop structure and timeline

To facilitate better understanding for the participants, the workshop was structured in three segments, including:

- Identification of the objectives: A presentation on the purposes of exploitation, a summary of the previous workshops, and findings from the shared pre-exploitation questionnaire was given.
- Group Discussions: Following the presentation, the participants were divided into 3 groups according to their expertise and in round table discussions addressed three main questions regarding the project's current state, future innovations, and Intellectual Property (IP) strategies. All findings were monitored using Miro to ensure all information is stored together and is accessible to everyone.
- Final remarks: The workshop ended with a short discussion on the summary of the findings from what partners had shared.

Figure 4 Group Discussion from 3rd Exploitation Workshop

Figure 5 Group Discussion from 3rd Exploitation Workshop

5.3 Summary of Group Discussions

During the group discussions, participants were divided based on work packages and partners' expertise to address each topic. The main objectives were reassessing the KERs, identifying new KERs (if needed), and defining future pathways. More specifically:

5.3.1 Group 1 - KER Validation

Participants: WP1 – Pilot region partners

Topic addressed: What are the key factors influencing the exploitation potential of existing KERs, including barriers, enablers, and their current market readiness?"

Discussion Points:

- What is the current TRL (Technology Readiness Level) of each KER?
- What are the main barriers stopping us from using/exploiting existing KERs or fully meeting them?
- What actions could enable us to exploit the met KERs? Are there any KERs that can potentially have a market impact? Which KERs have the highest market potential?
- What is the current market readiness level, and how can we meet the market readiness level? What limits us, and what can enable us to meet market readiness?

Findings:

Partner's discussions demonstrate that fully meeting the KERs is difficult to be achieved due to the amount of product production, as well as many legal barriers that limit the commercialisation of the production. It was highly observed that even though not a lot of things have changed in the past couple of years, the ground has been worked for public

authorities to explore more circular solutions, compared to linear solutions and that things are open for change. Many reports have been developed and addressed to DG Grow regarding the need of more sustainable farming products, such as bio-fertilisers. Significant achievement was the participation of DG GROW at P2Green's first cross-fertilisation Workshop. Partners appeared to be positive and emphasised the importance of grasping the momentum and pushing for change.

Another point discussed was the price difference between circular products and linear products, as linear products are cost-efficient since not all costs are considered. This makes public acceptance more difficult for circular products that must emphasise the overall benefits of their use to track attraction. "Seeing is believing," and this should be the best promotional approach to convince farmers and public authorities that the solutions suggested are effective and needed, based on actions taken so far, field visits have been proven a convincing strategy for the general public and public authorities to stand by the pilot regions' work.

Important mention was also given to the need to focus on the solution rather than the process, since the public's understanding of source separation can cause confusion and disbelief in the products/solutions' benefits. Hence, marketing should focus on the benefits of the solutions rather than their process.

Contrary to the solution-based approach that should be followed for the general public, partners also pointed out that it is important to share some technological processes with other small companies to promote the replication of their solutions, enhance the ecosystem, empower their overall market position, and united add pressure on big corporations.

5.3.2 Group 2 - New KERs Identification

Participants: WP4 & WP3 partners

Topic addressed: What new innovations can be commercialized, and what gaps in the bioeconomy value chain need to be filled to enable this?

Discussion Points:

- Are there any new or underutilized innovations in the project that we can use?
- What's missing in the bioeconomy value chain, and how can we address those gaps?
- What industry partners could help us bring these ideas to life?

Findings:

During the 2nd Exploitation Workshop, partners showed a lot of interest in a discussion regarding new innovations focusing on other bioeconomy gaps (see Chapter 4.3.2). During the 3rd Exploitation workshop, the opportunity was given to readdress the topic and discuss new potential solutions. During the discussion, partners emphasised the

need to fully utilise the project's existing innovations and explore other ways of using them. More specifically, they referred to the regulatory aspect, which, for the time being, limits the use of the developed technologies in the food sector and how those technologies could be applied in different frameworks. For instance, the exploration of overlooked opportunities in the Agri-Food sector could benefit from the use of this project's innovations. Such examples consist of grass growth in football fields and golf fields, or the use of P2Green's bio-fertilisers and reclaimed water technologies in the green decorative industry for flower growth.

Partners also emphasised the need to use the technologies developed, the learning process, and the positive outcomes of their use to educate students and new farmers, as well as public authorities, on the benefits of those solutions. Through the project's experiences and findings, the importance of embracing sustainable solutions should be addressed and promoted in educational frameworks to spark discussions and motivate young minds to work towards more sustainable solutions.

In addition, partners highlighted the importance of developing links between the countryside and cities where public authorities understand and support the efforts made by agriculturists to utilise wastewater and waste in general and support their actions by facilitating the transportation of waste and wastewater, as well as financially support their efforts with the contribution of the public through taxes.

Finally, partners mentioned the importance of public and private support from authorities and organisations in finding the best ways to utilise the developed technologies. For instance, until policy change is achieved, they could collaborate with other Agri-Food Sectors, as mentioned above, to utilise the products and solutions developed.

5.3.3 Group 3 - Pathway Definition

Participants: WP2 & WP5 partners

Topic addressed: What **IP strategies** and **commercialization pathways** are needed to advance key KERs?"

Discussion Points:

- What IP strategies (patents, open licensing, collaboration agreements) are necessary?
- Is the current path we are following sufficient? Is there something that could change or could be done to help move things forward?
- Should the KERs be modified, or are there any new KERs that should be addressed to help us meet the requirements for commercialization?
- What relevant action steps can be taken to address the IP topic and identify commercialization to meet end users?
- What are the next steps, and who is responsible for them?
- What funding or market entry opportunities are available for the KERs?

Findings:

Partners engaging in this discussion pointed out that intellectual property strategies should not be considered a priority by pilot regions, as the promotion of the technologies/solutions developed should and would benefit the replication and partnership extension of the pilot regions. According to them, what should be protected is the Replication/Innovation Platform, as this tool should also be commercialised and sold by the partners to other interested parties, to create an additional income stream.

In addition, through the help of public authorities, it is very important to raise awareness on the topic and present the farmers with existing alternatives, such as those developed in the project, and foster communication of the project's work. Engagement with farmer associations and education of the farmers on P2Green's practices would support the exploitation of the project and help engage farmers with the project's solutions, which would help raise the demand for sustainable products and raise the topic of reevaluating policies.

Moreover, this discussion highlighted the need to establish business models that would enable the solutions developed to be fully commercialised and also assist follower regions in following a proven model to make it easier for communities and governments to engage and support this initiative. Having effective business models that lead to commercialisation pathways would also allow partners to enhance their collaboration and promote the use of each other's solutions.

5.4 Comparative Analysis of Discussion Findings

In summary, despite the partners not being aware of the discussions unfolding in each group, they have come to common conclusions and contradicted one another based on their different points of view.

Overall, all partners highly believe that governance change on an EU level is of major importance, as relying on national regulations limits their possibilities for commercialisation of their technologies. This is because at a national level, governments depend on market demand to approve certain products, and hence, more awareness should be spread among communities and countries to raise interest in P2Green's solutions and increase demand. Actions towards this have been established as a great dialogue has sparked over the last few years on the topic, and P2Green partners are highly involved in drafting comparative reports that address the issue and prove the need for policy change.

Even more, all partners agree on the importance of developing an effective communication strategy that focuses primarily on the promotion of the solutions and their benefits. Emphasising the role of sustainable waste management, as well as the positives and benefits of the project's solutions, can increase public interest and strike demand.

Hence, new creative dissemination strategies are under development that would promote the benefits of those solutions for end users.

Highly important is also the partners' interest in exploring different Agricultural sectors that would allow the utilisation of P2Green's solutions. Exploring the application of these technologies outside the framework of food production increases the possibilities of innovation utilisation and overcomes challenges in government regulations and social acceptance.

Important mention was also given to Business Model development, as well as Intellectual Property rights. As per Deliverable 3.1 Report containing four circular business models (Lasthein, Ekstrand, Møller, Stieber, Sargsyan, 2025), four Circular Business Models have been developed for each pilot region and each product/technology. For the Swedish and German pilot region products, business models focusing on product sales have been established. In the case of Goldeimer's solution, since it consists of both product and service, the revenue streams have multiplied. In the case of the Spanish pilot region, the Business model focuses on a service-based income between the partners. Hence, this shows that partners' interest in business model development has already been addressed. As seen from the discussions made on the topic, the option of a business model for the replication platform has also been raised and has not been explored yet. Doing so would highly benefit partners and follower regions as more revenue streams can be developed.

On the Intellectual Property rights topic, conversations between partners were contradictory, as partners from different work packages had different views. Discussions between pilot region partners have shown that despite their willingness to share their technologies with follower regions and other associates, when it comes to external organisations, they would rather not share everything, as that would damage their market power. Partners from WP2 & WP5, when asked the same question, strongly expressed that IP rights are not necessary, as partners would like to share their knowledge with others and extend the cycle of sustainable practices. Yet it was more important to protect the Replication/Innovation Platform findings to promote service sales. Partners are yet to come to an agreement, but through further discussions, it became evident that on an internal level, technology sharing is important and welcome, while on an external level, more careful actions should be taken. This also concludes that more discussions need to be held between partners, and the corresponding actions should be taken.

5.5 Lessons learned from the 3rd Exploitation Workshop

Through the 3rd Exploitation Workshop, some gaps were identified, and some challenges occurred. As shown in the comparative analysis above, challenges regarding policy regulations and social acceptance are still core barriers to the exploitation of the P2Green solutions. Despite partners' efforts, these challenges have remained over the past years, but as partners state, this is a work in progress and these challenges are being addressed. Moreover, a misalignment was observed from the partners' point of view on Intellectual Property rights. As discussions during the workshop had not concluded,

follow-up meetings between work packages are scheduled to determine next steps and key actions.

5.6 Positive Outcomes from the 3rd Exploitation Workshop

Overall, the round table discussions facilitated the discussion process, as smaller groups built up dialogues and allowed participants to immerse themselves in their discussions. The specific group selections assigned to each topic were also beneficial for the participants to expand on topics directly related to their expertise and Know-How based on their role in the project.

Regarding the achievements of this Workshop, from the partners' feedback, it has been seen that all KERs are progressing at a steady pace and their full completion is expected by the end of the project. Moreover, a shift in partners' approach to the Exploitation of the project from research-focused to product/solution-focused shows that partners are looking beyond the scope of the project and are actively working towards the next steps. In addition, all challenges that had occurred during the discussions have helped identify the next steps that need to be taken, such as:

- Concluding on the strategic approach partners want to take on Intellectual Property rights, through bilateral discussions,
- Enhancing actions taken to achieve policy change; event participation, participation in EU open calls on topics related to P2Green, development of material directed to policy makers, etc.,
- Development of communication strategies focusing on social acceptance, showcasing primarily P2Green's solutions and their benefits,
- Exploring the possibility of developing an additional business model for the Replication/Innovation Platform,
- Exploring the possibilities of utilising P2Green's solutions in different sectors outside the food industry.

6 Exploitation Plan

To ensure full exploitation of the project beyond its life span, partners agreed on the development of an Exploitation Plan that would assure all, indicative and not, KERs are fully addressed and that actions that would promote the project's activities and results are taken. The Exploitation Plan leads partners in the development of their exploitation, it includes the KER identification, the KERs technology level assessment, and exploitation routes. It also explores a joint market analysis to identify the commercialisation potential and specify the required IP protection measures, which were addressed through the Exploitation Workshops. Finally, it provides an Exploitation Roadmap based on the project's current exploitative stage and ways forward.

6.1 KER identification

As part of the GA, partners agreed upon some indicative KERs as shown in Table 2 to initiate some actions towards exploitation. Based on the partner's input throughout all Exploitation Workshops, those KERs were enough to address all important topics for sufficient project exploitation, hence, partners' actions focused on meeting these KERs the best possible way. During the 1st Exploitation Workshop, partners had the opportunity to identify and discuss the KERs' purpose. They also had the opportunity to discuss whether they would like to move forward with these KERs and work towards their completion. As seen from the above summary (see Chapter 3), partners were fully able to comprehend the KERs' value and identify their meaning.

During the 1st Exploitation Workshop, partners also had the opportunity to decide on some initial approaches that would have led to the KERs' completion. These actions included the submission of the deliverables, partners' attendance in multiple events and conferences, the participation of P2GreenN in multiple cluster activities, the abstract and peer-reviewed article submissions, the drafting of documents and participation in open calls for policy change, and the dissemination of the project's actions amongst others.

6.2 KERs Technology Level Assessment

Since P2GreenN's KERs represent methodologies, governance frameworks and practical guides rather than tangible technologies, a standard Technology Readiness Level (TRL) scale cannot be directly applied. Progress percentages were therefore derived through a structured self-evaluation process: partner teams completed a dedicated survey prior to EW3 (May 2025) assessing their progress against agreed KER milestones, and results were reviewed and validated collectively during the workshop. Figures have been rounded to the nearest whole number for clarity. A score of 100% indicates full completion of all planned outputs associated with a given KER. *Figure 6* below provides an overview of progress across all seven KERs as of M30.

Note: figures reflect M30 assessment; updated scores to be confirmed at EW4 (M42).

Figure 6 KER progress as of M30 (May 2025). Percentages are based on a structured self-evaluation survey completed by partner teams prior to EW3 and validated collectively during the workshop. Figures rounded to the nearest whole number. Target: 100% completion by M48 (November 2026).

KER1: Development of Blueprints from P2GreenN Pilot Regions Progress: 70% | Lead: WP1 | Lead partners: BIOAZUL, SLU, KWB

Key pending deliverable	D1.4 -Blueprints from the three pilot regions (M48)
Specific actions	Finalise pilot documentation across the three pilot regions (Gotland, North German Plain, La Axarquia), incorporating lessons learned from the full project lifecycle. Organise field visits and knowledge exchange sessions with follower regions to validate blueprint applicability in new contexts. Produce accessible communication products (factsheets, visual summaries) tailored to farmers, public authorities and replication actors. Present and exchange findings at the 4th cross-fertilisation workshop (M38, T1.4).
Responsible partners (blueprint development & replication)	Bioazul, SLU, KWB and all other pilot region partners
Timeline	M37-M48

Post-project sustainability	Blueprints actively used across the three pilot regions (Gotland, North German Plain, La Axarquía) as operational references for circular N&P flow implementation; to be publicly hosted on p2green.eu Open Resources and shared through CCRI and ESPP networks to support replication by follower regions and other EU initiatives.
------------------------------------	--

KER2: Methodologies and Criteria for Data Collection in P2Green Progress: 66% | Lead: WP2 | Lead partners: SLU, LUKE

Key pending action	Compile and document lessons learned from RP2 and RP3 data collection experience as reported in D2.4 (Policy brief summarising trade-offs and absolute sustainability impacts)
Specific actions	Compile and synthesise lessons learned from RP2 and RP3 data collection activities across all pilot regions, as documented in D2.4. Produce a concise, practitioner-friendly methods reference document suitable for external audiences and future R&D projects. Submit findings to peer-reviewed journals and present monitoring methodology outcomes at scientific conferences and cluster events.
Responsible partners (data methodology development & knowledge transfer)	SLU, LUKE, IGZ, CETAQUA
Timeline	M37-M48
Post-project sustainability	Methodology to be integrated into the Innovation Platform as a reusable data framework; available to future R&D projects building on P2Green findings

KER3:Toolbox for Social Acceptance Progress: 73% | Lead: WP3 | Lead partners: IRS, SUSTCHEM

Key pending action	Synthesis of findings into an accessible, reusable toolbox format
Specific actions	Synthesise social acceptance findings from all three pilot regions and four follower regions into a structured, reusable toolbox format, including region-specific insights on barriers, drivers and stakeholder engagement strategies. Develop stakeholder-specific factsheets and visual communication materials targeting farmers and farmers associations, public authorities, municipalities and civil society . Present toolbox findings at EW4 (M42) and the Final Conference (M47), and integrate lessons into RP3 dissemination campaigns led by CIP and MOVERIM.
Responsible partners (toolbox development & social acceptance outreach)	IRS, ENPC, IAAC, SUSTCHEM, CBS, CIP, MOVERIM
Timeline	M37-M48
Post-project sustainability	Package as open-access resource on p2green.eu; share through EWA, IWA and ESPP networks; applicable as a methodology reference in future circular sanitation projects across Europe

KER4: Development of a Sustainable Governance Framework for N&P Management Progress: 75% | Lead: WP4 | Lead partners: CBS, ICLEI, ENPC, HCU, Ville de Paris

Key pending deliverables	D4.5 - EU-wide governance recommendations (M47)
Specific actions	Deliver governance framework training sessions in the three pilot regions (M34, T4.3). Conduct follower region workshops to transfer governance guidelines and support local implementation (M36, T4.3). Draft D4.5, the EU-wide governance recommendations, consolidating findings from all four WP4 tasks into actionable policy guidance. Present

recommendations at DG ENV and DG GROW events, contribute to relevant EC open consultation processes, and distribute materials through EurEau, ESPP and Copa Cogeca networks.

Responsible partners (governance framework development & policy advocacy)	SUSTCHEM, CBS, ICLEI, ENPC, HCU, KRTK/IRS, Ville de Paris
Timeline	M37-M47
Post-project sustainability	Submit recommendations formally to EC (DG ENV, DG GROW); distribute through EurEau, ESPP and Copa Cogeca networks; use as advocacy material for regulatory acceptance of bio-based fertilisers

KER5: P2Green Replication/Innovation Platform and Action Plans *Progress: 69% | Lead: WP5 | Lead partners: IAAC, CERTH, IGZ*

Key pending deliverable	D5.8 Replication Action Plans for Follower Regions
Specific actions	Finalise the commercialisation decision for the Replication Platform (IAAC, WP5, D5.8), determining whether to pursue a commercial or open-access model. Engage follower regions in active use of the Replication Platform and present platform capabilities at EW4 (M42).
Responsible partners (platform development & commercialisation)	IAAC, CERTH, IRIDRA, IGZ, MOVERIM (commercial pathway advisory)
Timeline	M37–M47
Post-project sustainability	Two platforms will continue operating post-project. The Innovation Platform (IGZ, WP7, D7.2), hosted on p2green.eu and mirrored on Zenodo, will serve as a permanent open-access knowledge repository for project outputs and datasets. The Replication Platform (IAAC, WP5, D5.8) will remain available to follower

regions as an operational tool for replicating P2GreenN circular solutions beyond project closure at M48

KER6: Regional Replication Action Plans *Progress: 63% | Lead: WP5 | Lead partners: IAAC, IRIDRA*

Key pending deliverable	D5.8 -Replication Action Plans for follower regions (M47)
Specific actions	Complete feasibility studies in all four follower regions (Italy, France, Hungary, Greece), building on D5.4 findings to assess technical, regulatory and socio-economic conditions for replication. Validate and finalise one Regional Action Plan per follower region (D5.8), co-developed with local stakeholders and informed by pilot region blueprints. Present and discuss outcomes and replication pathways at the 2nd EU-wide virtual workshop (M38), EW4 (M42) and the Final Conference (M47).
Responsible partners (replication action plan development & follower region implementation)	IAAC, IRIDRA (Italy), ENPC/Ville de Paris (France), KRTK (Hungary), CERTH (Greece)
Timeline	M37-M47
Post-project sustainability	Action Plans to serve as operational playbooks for follower regions post-project; shared openly via p2green.eu and CCRI; intended as a basis for future Horizon Europe applications in follower countries

KER7: Guide on How to Initiate, Manage and Scale Circular Solutions *Progress: 68% | Lead: WP5 | Lead partners: ICLEI, CBS, CERTH, Transition ApS*

Key pending deliverable	D5.6 - Knowledge exchange workshops report (M37)
--------------------------------	--

Specific actions	Deliver remaining capacity building workshops in follower regions as part of the knowledge exchange programme (D5.6), ensuring all planned sessions are completed and outcomes documented. The D5.9 Blueprint is planned to be presented at the 2nd Round of National Workshops with follower regions, at the EU-wide workshop at the European Week of Regions and Cities 2025; it is publicly accessible on Zenodo and the P2GreenN Innovation Platform. Submit D5.6 and present the D5.9 Blueprint - the comprehensive guide on initiating, managing and scaling circular solutions - at the 2nd EU-wide virtual workshop (M38), EW4 (M42) and the Final Conference (M47), including a dedicated session on P2GreenN business models and circular solutions. Distribute the Blueprint through CCRI, ESPP and RBA networks to maximise reach among practitioners and future project consortia.
Responsible partners (guide development & capacity building)	ICLEI (lead), CBS, CERTH, Transition, CIP
Timeline	M37-M47
Post-project sustainability	Blueprint openly accessible on p2green.eu and Zenodo; adaptable for use in future bioeconomy and circular sanitation projects; ICLEI to integrate findings into their urban sustainability programmes

Based on the above evaluation, it is evident that over the past 36 months, significant and well-documented progress has been made across all seven KERs. All KERs are on track for full completion by M48. The focus for the final reporting period (RP3) is on finalising remaining deliverables, expanding reach to target stakeholders, and securing post-project sustainability for each result. The Exploitation Roadmap in Section 7 translates these priorities into specific, time-bound actions with named responsible partners.

6.3 Exploitation Routes

Three main exploitation routes have been identified for P2GreenN's KERs, based on partner discussions across all three Exploitation Workshops. These routes are not

mutually exclusive; several KERs are being pursued through more than one channel simultaneously. The diagram below maps each route to the KERs it addresses, the key channels being used, and the lead partners responsible.

IP & legal strategy (cross-cutting — all KERs)

Agreement on background IP grants all partners co-ownership of data, know-how and information produced within the project. Discussions on specific technology ownership and patent filing are ongoing, with a finalised IP strategy to be documented before project closure at M48. A dedicated IP strategy document will be finalised in consultation with all WP leads.

Policy and regulatory advocacy is the primary route for KER3, KER4 and KER6, given that the current EU regulatory framework restricts the commercialisation of bio-fertilisers derived from human excreta in most member states. Partners are actively engaging with DG ENV and DG GROW, contributing to EC open calls, and working with EurEau, ESPP and Copa Cogeca to build the evidence base for regulatory change. National-level experimental approvals already in place in Germany, Spain and Sweden provide proof-of-concept to support this advocacy.

Commercial development is the primary route for KER1 and KER5. Four Circular Business Model Canvases (CBMCs) have been developed through D3.1, and discussions are underway regarding a fifth CBMC for the Replication Platform. Specific commercial pathways being explored include KRAV organic certification by the Gotland pilot, BREEAM building certification integration for the German urine treatment technology, and market entry via the countries where Aurin fertiliser is already approved (Austria, Switzerland, France).

Knowledge transfer and open access is the primary route for KER2, KER5 and KER7. P2Green's outputs are publicly accessible through Zenodo (25 publications to date), the Innovation Platform, and the p2green.eu Open Resources section. Active participation in CCRI, ESPP and RBA clusters ensures peer learning and co-advocacy with related EU initiatives. Capacity building workshops across follower regions (D5.6, M37) further extend the project's reach beyond the consortium.

IP and legal strategy is a cross-cutting priority for all KERs. The current consortium agreement grants all partners co-ownership of data, know-how and information produced within P2Green. Discussions on specific technology ownership and patent filing are ongoing, with decisions with a finalised IP strategy to be documented before project closure at M48.

6.4 Joint market analysis and IP protection strategies

The joint market analysis and IP protection strategy for P2Green's KERs are addressed in full under Section 6.3 (Exploitation Routes) above, which maps each exploitation route, including commercial development pathways and IP and legal strategy, to the relevant KERs, responsible partners and specific actions being pursued. Key milestones and timelines are further detailed in the Exploitation Roadmap (Section 7).

7 Exploitation Roadmap

The Exploitation Roadmap below consolidates all planned exploitation actions for the final reporting period (RP3, M37-M48). Figure 7 provides a timeline overview of when each action takes place; Extended table presents the full detail per task, including responsible partners, timeline, success indicator and current status.

Figure 7 P2Green Exploitation Roadmap (M12-M48). Red line = current period (M30, May 2025). Dashed lines guide from task name to bar position.

Extended Table Figure 8 follows on the next page.

Note: Detailed partner-level exploitation commitments and post-project plans will be documented in full in D6.2 (Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, due M48).

Project Number:
Project Acronym:

101081883
P2Green
Deliverable 6.4

Task	KER(s)	Responsible partners	Timeline	Success indicator	Status
Policy Policy event attendance & EC advocacy	KER3, KER4	WP3, WP4 SUSTCHEM, CBS, ICLEI, NUIM, ENPC, HCU	M12– M48	≥5 policy events attended; contributions to ≥2 EC open calls on circular N&P	● Ongoing
Policy Participation in EC open calls on policy recommendations	KER4	All WPs Lead: SUSTCHEM, CBS	M12– M48	≥2 formal submissions to EC consultations on circular economy / bio-fertilisers	● Ongoing
Dissemination Farmers' summits & agri events	KER1, KER2	WP1, WP2 BIOAZUL, S360, IGZ, TROPS, Agualytics	M18– M48	≥3 farmer-facing events; documented reach to farming associations	● Ongoing
Dissemination Scientific conferences & publications	All KERs	All WPs Lead: WP2, WP3	M12– M48	≥4 peer-reviewed publications; ≥6 conference presentations in RP3	● Ongoing
Dissemination Stakeholder communication campaign (per target group)	KER3, KER7	WP6 CIP, MOVERIM	M12– M48	Materials produced for ≥3 stakeholder groups; social media & website KPIs met	● Ongoing
IP & legal IP strategy discussion & finalisation	All KERs	WP7, All partners Lead: AGRATHAER, IGZ	M24– M40	Agreement reached on IP ownership per KER; IP strategy documented in D7.1	● In progress
Commercial 5th CBMC for Replication Platform	KER5	WP3, WP5 CBS, ICLEI, CERTH, Triodos Bank	M24– M40	CBMC completed; commercialisation vs open access decision taken	● In progress
Submitted D1.4 — Blueprints from the three pilot regions	KER1	WP1 Lead: BIOAZUL, SLU, KWB Partners: IGZ, S360, VunaNexus, TROPS	M30 ✓	Deliverable submitted M30; blueprints validated across three pilot regions	● Submitted
IP & legal IP acquisition & patent filing (where applicable)	KER1, KER5	WP7, WP1, WP5 AGRATHAER, IGZ, VunaNexus, CERTH	M40– M47	Patent applications filed where agreed; IP strategy document finalised	● Planned
Deliverable D5.4 — Feasibility studies for follower regions	KER6	WP5 Lead: IRIDRA Partners: CERTH, IAAC, KRTK/IRS	M6–M40	Four feasibility studies completed, one per follower region (IT, FR, HU, GR)	● In progress
Deliverable D3.8 — Final legislative report	KER4	WP3 Lead: SUSTCHEM, UCD, NUIM Partners: AGRATHAER, ENPC	M36– M42	Deliverable submitted; final recommendations on legislative pathways delivered	● Planned
Event EW4 — 4th Exploitation Workshop (online)	All KERs	WP6 CIP, MOVERIM, All partners	M42	≥30 participants; KER progress reviewed; updated TRL% confirmed; partner actions logged	● Planned
Deliverable D4.5 — EU-wide governance recommendations	KER4	WP4 Lead: ICLEI, CBS Partners: ENPC, KRTK/IRS	M47	Deliverable submitted; distributed to EC (DG ENV, DG GROW) and policy networks	● Planned
Deliverable D5.8 — Replication Action Plans for follower regions	KER5, KER6	WP5 Lead: IAAC Partners: IRIDRA, CERTH, KRTK/IRS	M46	4 Regional Action Plans delivered (one per follower region: HU, IT, FR, GR)	● Planned
Event Final International Conference (D6.6)	All KERs	WP6 Lead: CIP, All partners	M47	≥100 external participants; all KERs presented; post-project pathways communicated	● Planned
Deliverable D6.2 — Final Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Plan	All KERs	WP6 CIP, MOVERIM	M48	Deliverable submitted; full exploitation record documented	● Planned

Figure 8 P2Green Exploitation Roadmap. Written from M30 perspective. Status: green = ongoing, orange = in progress, dark grey = submitted, light grey = planned.

8 Outlook: 4th Exploitation Workshop, online: Evaluation of Exploitation achievements

The 4th and final Exploitation Workshop (EW4) will be held online in June 2026 (M42), bringing together all consortium partners to review the project's exploitation achievements ahead of closure in November 2026. The workshop is structured around five main agenda areas, as shown in Figure 9 below. All outcomes, decisions and lessons learned from EW4 will be incorporated into the Final Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan (D6.2, M48).

Figure 9 EW4 agenda overview, Online, June 2026 (M42). Lead: CIP & Moverim

9 Conclusion

As part of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy, WP6 has held 3 Exploitation Workshops aiming at the identification, completion, and advancement of the KERs as stated in the GA. Throughout these past 2,5 years, partners managed to identify all KERs and take actionable steps toward their completion. Each WP has worked on the completion of their assigned KER and has made sufficient progress over the 30 months, estimating their full completion by the end of the project. Even though there is still work to be done, partners have progressed and managed to fully understand what exploitation means. As a result, they can fully understand challenges and pivot towards other solutions or actions to overcome the barriers.

Additionally, an Exploitation Plan has been given above, outlining the exploitation progress so far and evaluating the KERs technology level advancement. Through clear exploitation routes, the next steps have been identified, and they will facilitate the overall exploitation of the project. From the findings of the exploitation strategies and exploitation workshops, it has been shown that the most important exploitation topics that need addressing and are the most challenging ones to meet are social acceptance, policy changes, acknowledging P2Green solutions, and the IP strategies that need to be decided.

With the completion of KERs and their further exploitation to the associated stakeholders, through the exploitation routes mentioned above, the P2Green consortium will have achieved the project's anticipated exploitation for its lifespan. Pilot regions will then be able to forward the developed blueprints to follower regions for replication and will have sufficient tools to establish viable companies. Project partners will also be able to address regulation gaps and drive change at a European level and even promote the development of additional projects that would expand the current research and help enable future sustainable solutions.

All in all, from identifying the KERs, setting strategies to achieve maximum exploitation, to suggesting and fully leveraging new and existing innovations, partners have enabled themselves to look beyond the project's scope and search for future opportunities. Overall, the workshops achieved their goal, to enable partners to take their research to the next stage and search for market/ commercialisation opportunities, addressing regulatory gaps, and considering and working toward IP strategies. Partners now look forward to the progression of their efforts in the follower regions and aim to expand their network with other organisations who are willing to expand towards more sustainable circular solutions.

10 References

Beblek, A., D7.1 IPR strategy P2GreeN, 2024

Cabrera, D., & Cabrera, L. (2018). Why You Should Map: The Science Behind Visual Mapping. Cornell White Paper #1. https://www.academia.edu/45435508/Why_You_Should_Map_The_Science_Behind_Visual_Mapping

Czarnik et al, D3.7 “Scoping review” describing the status of the legislative framework 2023, P2GreeN Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

Ganglo, C. et al., D2.1. P2GreeN guidelines for methodologies and templates for data collection, 2023, P2GreeN Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

Joveniaux, Obersteg, Shakya, Peters, Jaber, Taxonomy of governance frameworks in Europe, learnings from the St-Vincent-de-Paul project and consolidated recommendations for the P2GreeN governance framework. Part A: Study and provisional recommendations from the case of Saint-Vincent-de-Paul (Paris, France). Part B: Analysis and provisional recommendations of case studies, 2024, P2GreeN Consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

Lasthein, Ekstrand, Møller, Stieber, Sargsyan, D3.1, Report containing four circular business models, 2025, P2GreeN consortium. Accessible at www.p2green.eu

Löhr, K., Weinhardt, M., & Sieber, S. (2020). The “World Café” as a Participatory Method for Collecting Qualitative Data. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406920916976> (Original work published 2020)

Contact

Programme Coordinator:

agrathaer GmbH

Eberswalder Straße 84, 15374 Müncheberg

Tel.: +49 33432 82 149

Info@agrathaer.de

www.p2green.eu

www.facebook.com/p2greenHorizonEU

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/p2green-horizon-eu-72aba1259/>

www.instagram.com/p2green/

www.twitter.com/P2green_Horizon

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No°101081883.
Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only
and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the
European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.